

Homoisoflavones. Part—IV. Further Synthetical Experiments

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The method of Farkas *et al.* has been extended to synthesise a number of homoisoflavones from *o*-hydroxy dihydro chalcones by ethyl formate—sodium metal.

THE acid catalysed condensation of *p*-anisaldehyde with 5,7-dimethoxychromanone gave eucomin dimethyl ether (I) which on isomerisation with Raney nickel¹ gave the homoisoflavone (II) which has already been synthesised by Farkas and coworkers² by the action of ethyl formate and sodium metal on the dihydrochalcone (III). (II) on hydrogenation over Pd-C in ethyl acetate gave 3,9-dihydroeucomindimethyl ether which was also reported by Farkas *et al.*³ Several other homoisoflavones (Va-c) were prepared by the isomerisation reaction, their spectral properties are given in the experimental procedure. It may be emphasised that in this isomerisation reaction the quality of Raney nickel appears to be critical. A two month aged sample usually brought about the isomerisation smoothly and quickly. In some cases, dihydrohomoisoflavones were encountered as obvious byproducts.

tion to give homoisoflavone with warm acetic acid (cf. F. Eiden and W. Luft⁴). 2-Hydroxyhomoisoflavanone showed chelated carbonyl group ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1660 cm^{-1}). This acetal should exist in the conformation shown below 2-OH in *quasi*-axial and 3-benzyl in *quasi*-equatorial position; the ready H^+ catalysed diaxial elimination of water is therefore accountable so as to give the homoisoflavone.

As referred above, the ethyl formate route to the homoisoflavones as used by Farkas *et al.*³ have now been examined and extended in order to study the general applicability of this reaction. In general, the dihydrochalcones (VIIa-e) gave homoisoflavones (IXa-e) in good yield and in one case (VIIb) we isolated hemiacetal (VIII) which smoothly underwent β -elimina-

Ethyl formate may also be replaced by ethyl orthoformate (*vide* experimental). The dihydrochalcones (VIIa-e) in these experiments were secured by the catalytic hydrogenation of chalcones (VIa-e). We have also secured several other dihydrochalcones by Hoesch condensation of appropriate arylpropionitriles with polyhydric phenols. This route appears very suitable for the synthesis of polyhydroxy dihydrochalcones as illustrated below and hence is of promise in the synthesis of polyhydroxyhomoisoflavonoids. Their utility is being examined.

$C_{19}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 69.92; H, 5.56%; (ν C=O 1665 cm^{-1}).

7,8-Dimethoxy-3-(4'-methylbenzylidene) chroman-4-one :

As above, a mixture of freshly distilled *p*-tolu-aldehyde (0.45 g), 7,8-dimethoxychroman-4-one (0.5 g), conc. hydrochloric acid (5 drops) and absolute alcohol (15 ml) was heated on a water bath for 7 hours. Processing as usual, 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(4'-methylbenzylidene)chroman-4-one was obtained as shining needles from methanol, m.p. 129-30°. (Found: C, 73.52; H, 5.45. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 73.53; H, 5.85%; (ν C=O 1665 cm^{-1}).

Experimental

All melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer Model 237. The NMR spectrum was recorded on Varian A-60 instrument and in deuteriochloroform with TMS as internal standard (Chemical shifts are expressed in τ values and J in cps).

5, 7-Dimethoxy-3-(4'-methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one (I) : (Eucomin dimethyl ether).

5, 7-Dimethoxychroman-4-one^{27a} (0.4 g), freshly distilled *p*-anisaldehyde (0.3), concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 drops) were added in that order to absolute alcohol (15 ml) and refluxed for 6 hours. After the reaction was complete, ethanol (90%) was distilled off and ethyl acetate (5 ml) was added. On cooling and scratching 5,7-dimethoxy-3-(4'-methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one was obtained as yellow solid which crystallised from ethanol-ethyl acetate mixture in yellow needles, m.p. 144-45° (lit.⁴, m.p. 141-44°). (Found: C, 69.91; H, 5.61. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$: C, 69.93; H, 5.50%; (ν C=O 1660 cm^{-1}).

5,7,4'-Trimethoxyhomoisoflavone (II) :

A two month aged sample of Raney nickel (about 0.5 ml sediment) was added to a solution of 5,7-dimethoxy-3-(4'-methoxybenzylidene)chroman-4-one (0.5 g) in dry xylene (15 ml). About 5 ml of xylene was distilled off to ensure the complete removal of alcohol from the catalyst. The mixture was then refluxed for 5 hours under anhydrous condition, cooled, filtered and the catalyst washed with xylene (5 ml $\times$ 2). The combined filtrate and washings were concentrated to 1-2 ml under reduced pressure. The oil so obtained on cooling and scratching gave a white solid of 5,7,4'-trimethoxyhomoisoflavone which on crystallisation from methanol gave needles, m.p. 114-15° (lit.², m.p. 114-15°). (Found: C, 69.92; H, 5.30. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$: C, 69.93; H, 5.50%; (ν C=O 1640 cm^{-1}).

3,9-Dihydroeucomindimethyl ether (IV) :

5,7-Dimethoxy-3-(4'-methoxybenzylidene)chroman-4-one (I) (0.2 g) in ethylacetate (20 ml) was hydrogenated over Pd-C (0.1 g; 10%). After the required volume of hydrogen was absorbed, the solution was filtered and ethyl acetate was distilled off under reduced pressure. A liquid compound was obtained which solidified on cooling. It was crystallised from petroleum ether in colourless needles, m.p. 79-80° (lit.², m.p. 80°); (ν C=O 1670 cm^{-1}).

7,8-Dimethoxyhomoisoflavone (Va) :

In a similar manner 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(benzylidene) chroman-4-one (0.25 g) was isomerised into 7,8-dimethoxyhomoisoflavone as a colourless solid which crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 119-120°. (Found: C, 73.51; H, 6.04. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 73.53; H, 5.85%; (ν C=O 1640 cm^{-1}).

7,8-Dimethoxy-3-(benzylidene)chroman-4-one :

Prepared by refluxing a mixture of 7,8-dimethoxychroman-4-one (1.04 g), benzaldehyde (0.79 g), concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 drops) and absolute alcohol (20 ml) as yellow solid. On crystallisation from methanol 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(benzylidene)chroman-4-one was obtained as shining yellow needles, m.p. 112-13°. (Found: C, 72.94; H, 5.54. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 72.96; H, 5.44%; (ν C=O 1665 cm^{-1}).

7,8,4'-Trimethoxyhomoisoflavone (Vb) :

In the similar manner 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(4'-methoxybenzylidene)chroman-4-one (0.25 g) was isomerised with Raney nickel (0.5 ml) in dry xylene into 7,8,4'-trimethoxyhomoisoflavone as a colourless solid which crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 108-110°. (Found: C, 69.91; H, 5.60. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 69.92; H, 5.56%; (ν C=O 1640 cm^{-1}).

7,8-Dimethoxy-3-(4'-methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one :

As before, a mixture of *p*-anisaldehyde (0.21 g), 7,8-dimethoxychroman-4-one (0.20 g), conc. hydrochloric acid (5 drops) in absolute alcohol (15 ml) was heated on a water bath for 8 hours. Processing as usual, the yellow needles of 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(4'-methoxybenzylidene)chroman-4-one were obtained from methanol, m.p. 127-28°. (Found: C, 69.91; H, 5.56.

7,8-Dimethoxy-4'-methylhomoisoflavone (Vc) :

Prepared by isomerisation of 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(4'-methylbenzylidene)chroman-4-one (0.25 g) as white needles from methanol, m.p. 119-20°. (Found: C, 73.53; H, 5.86. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 73.53; H, 5.85%; (ν C=O 1640 cm^{-1}).

2'-Hydroxy- ω -benzylacetophenone (VIIa) :**Method I :**

2'-Hydroxybenzalacetophenone⁷ (5 g) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (20 ml) and hydrogenated in the presence of palladised charcoal (0.1 g; 10%) at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. The total uptake of hydrogen was 575 ml in about 8 hours. Filtration and evaporation of the solvent gave the dihydrochalcone as an oil which distilled at 155–58°/2 mm. (Found: C, 79.59; H, 6.35. C₁₅H₁₄O₂ requires C, 79.62; H, 6.24%).

Method II :

Phenol (1.8 g) and β -(phenyl)propionitrile¹⁰ (2.65 g) were dissolved in dry ether (40 ml). The mixture was cooled to 0° and treated with freshly fused zinc chloride (3 g). A slow continuous stream of dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed in till it was fully saturated and then the mixture left in an ice chest overnight. The separated ketimine hydrochloride was washed with dry ether (5×25 ml) and decomposed by boiling with water (15 ml) for 1 hour. The mixture was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (MgSO₄). The ether was distilled off and the residual liquid was distilled at 153–158°/2 mm. (Found: C, 79.60; H, 6.30. C₁₅H₁₄O₂ requires C, 79.62; H, 6.24%).

2-Hydroxyhomoisoflavanone :**Method I :**

The foregoing dihydrochalcone (2.3 g) was dissolved in dry freshly distilled ethyl formate and added slowly to powdered sodium (0.5 g) when a reaction set in. The reaction was allowed to proceed vigorously and yet kept under control by dipping the flask in ice cold water from time to time. After half an hour the reaction subsided and the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. The excess of sodium was decomposed by treating the mixture with ethanol. Subsequently concentrated hydrochloric acid was added and the mixture warmed on water bath for 15 minutes which resulted in the separation of a crystalline solid. Water was added to the reaction mixture and it was extracted with ether. The ether solution was dried (MgSO₄) and evaporated to give 2-hydroxyhomoisoflavanone as a white solid, m.p. 142–43° which crystallised from ethanol as needles, m.p. 143–44°. (Found: C, 75.86; H, 5.30. C₁₅H₁₂O₃ requires C, 75.88; H, 5.13%); (ν C=O 1660 cm⁻¹).

Method II :

The foregoing dihydrochalcone (2.3 g) was dissolved in freshly distilled ethyl orthoformate and added slowly to it powdered sodium (0.5 g) when a reaction set in. On working up in the usual manner 2-hydroxyhomoisoflavanone was obtained as a white solid which crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 143–44° (no depression in mixed melting point).

Homoisoflavone (IXa) :

The above solid (0.5 g) was taken in glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and refluxed for 2 hours. Then the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice affording homoisoflavone as a white solid (0.4 g) which crystallised from methanol in shining colourless needles, m.p. 112–13° (no depression in mixed melting point on admixture with authentic specimen¹²; the i.r. spectra identical). (Found: C, 80.70; H, 5.38. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₂O₂: C, 81.34; H, 5.12%); (ν C=O 1640 cm⁻¹). NMR τ 6.12 (s, CH₂) τ 1.7–2.7 (multiplet aromatic H).

2'-Hydroxy-4'-methoxy-4-methylbenzalacetophenone (VIb) :

A solution of sodium hydroxide (22 ml; 50%) was added to a mixture of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (8.3 g) and *p*-tolualdehyde (5.5 g) in ethanol (15 ml). On warming and stirring of the reaction mixture for some time, a yellow solid was obtained. This was collected and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid to give 2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-4-methylbenzalacetophenone (4.2 g) which crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 117–18°. (Found: C, 75.96; H, 6.01. C₁₇H₁₆O₃ requires C, 75.97; H, 6.14%); (ν C=O 1620 cm⁻¹).

2'-Hydroxy-4'-methoxy-4-methyl- ω -benzylacetophenone (VIIb) :

A solution of the above chalcone (5.0 g) in ethyl acetate was hydrogenated in the presence of palladised charcoal (0.1 g; 10%) till no further gas was consumed at atmospheric pressure. On working up in the usual way the dihydro compound was obtained as colourless oil which distilled at 180°/2 mm. (Found: C, 75.52; H, 6.70. C₁₇H₁₈O₃ requires C, 75.53; H, 6.71%); (ν C=O 1630 cm⁻¹).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised in acetic acid in light red needles, m.p. 215–16°. (Found: N, 12.43; C₂₃H₂₂O₆N₄ requires N, 12.44%).

2-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-4'-methylhomoisoflavanone (VIII) :

As before the above dihydro compound (2.7 g) was taken in ethyl formate and added slowly to powdered sodium (1.0 g). Proceeding in the usual way a brown gum was obtained. This was chromatographed on alumina in benzene to give 2-hydroxy-7-methoxy-4'-methylhomoisoflavanone which crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m.p. 170–71°. (Found: C, 72.70; H, 5.57. C₁₈H₁₇O₄ requires C, 72.72; H, 5.72%); (ν C=O 1660 cm⁻¹). The same result was obtained with ethyl orthoformate and sodium metal.

7-Methoxy-4'-methylhomoisoflavone (IXb) :

The above compound (0.2 g) was taken in glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and refluxed for 3 hours. The

reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into crushed ice, when a white solid separated. 7-Methoxy-4'-methylhomoisoflavone crystallised from methanol in white needles, m.p. 113° (lit.^{1,2}, m.p. 113-14°). (Found : C, 77.10; H, 5.80. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₆O₃ : C, 77.12; H, 5.75%); (ν C=O 1640 cm⁻¹).

2'-Hydroxy-4-methyl- ω -benzylacetophenone (VIIId) :

2'-Hydroxy-4-methylbenzalacetophenone (5 g) in ethyl acetate (20 ml) was hydrogenated in the presence of palladised charcoal (0.1 g; 10%). On working up, the dihydro chalcone was obtained as colourless oil which distilled at 160°/2 mm. (Found : C, 79.95; H, 6.80. C₁₆H₁₆O₂ requires C, 79.97, 6.71%); (ν C=O 1630 cm⁻¹).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 194-95°. (Found : C, 62.82; H, 4.72; N, 13.31. C₂₂H₂₀O₅N₄ requires C, 62.85; H, 4.80; N, 13.33%).

4'-Methylhomotsoflavone (IXd) :

The above dihydrochalcone (1.7 g) was dissolved in freshly distilled ethyl formate (10 ml) and added to powdered sodium (0.5 g). On working up in the usual manner a brown gum was obtained which was chromatographed over alumina in benzene. 4'-Methylhomoisoflavone was obtained as a white solid (0.8 g) which crystallised from ethanol in shining white needles, m.p. 90-91° (lit.^{1,2}, m.p. 90-91°). (Found : C, 81.48; H, 6.10. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₆O₂ : C, 81.58; H, 5.64%); (ν C=O 1640 cm⁻¹).

2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy- ω -benzylacetophenone (VIIe) :

Prepared by catalytic hydrogenation of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzalacetophenone (5 g)³ in ethyl acetate (10 ml) and palladised charcoal (0.1 g; 10%) as an oil which distilled at 181-83°/3 mm.

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised in acetic acid as needles, m.p. 196-97°. (Found : C, 60.52; H, 5.02; N, 12.83. C₂₂H₂₀O₅N₄ requires C, 60.54; H, 4.62; N, 12.84%).

4'-Methoxyhomotsoflavone (IXe) :

The above dihydrochalcone (1.7 g) was dissolved in freshly distilled ethyl orthoformate (15 ml) and added slowly to powdered sodium (0.5 g). On working up in the usual manner a brown gum was obtained which was chromatographed over alumina using benzene as eluent. The homoisoflavone was obtained as a colourless solid which crystallised from methanol in white shining needles, m.p. 94-95° (lit.^{1,2}, m.p. 94-95°). (Found : C, 76.64; H, 5.48. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₄O₃ : C, 76.69; H, 5.30%); (ν C=O 1640 cm⁻¹).

2'-Hydroxy-4,4'-dimethoxy- ω -benzylacetophenone (VIIc) :

Method I :

Prepared by catalytic hydrogenation of 2'-hydroxy-4,4'-dimethoxybenzalacetophenone⁹ (5 g) in ethyl acetate (10 ml) over palladised charcoal (0.1 g; 10%) as oil which distilled at 203-205°/1.8 mm. (Found : C, 79.89; H, 6.82. C₁₆H₁₆O₂ requires C, 79.97; H, 6.71%); (ν C=O 1630 cm⁻¹).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised as deep yellow needles from acetic acid, m.p. 207-208°. (Found : N, 11.98. C₂₃H₂₂O₇N₄ requires N, 12.01%).

Method II :

Resorcinol monomethyl ether (1.2 g) and β -(4-methoxyphenyl) propionitrile¹¹ (1.65 g) were dissolved in dry ether (35 ml). The mixture was cooled to 0°C and treated with freshly fused zinc chloride (3 g). It was fully saturated with dry hydrogen chloride gas and left in ice chest overnight. On working up in the usual manner a liquid compound was obtained which distilled at 203-206°/1.7 mm. (Found : C, 79.88; H, 6.75. C₁₆H₁₆O₂ requires C, 79.97; H, 6.71%); (ν C=O 1630 cm⁻¹).

7,4'-Dimethoxyhomoisoflavone (IXc) :

A solution of the above dihydrochalcone (1.4 g) in dry ethyl orthoformate was added to powdered sodium (0.15 g). On working up a brown gum was obtained which was chromatographed over alumina in benzene and 7,4'-dimethoxyhomoisoflavone was obtained as a colourless solid which crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 97-98° (lit.^{1,2}, m.p. 97-98°). (Found : C 72.76; H, 5.53. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₆O₄ : C, 72.96; H, 5.44%); (ν C=O 1640 cm⁻¹).

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